

Newly Developed Stainless Steel Fiber by Resin Coated Coiled Sheet Slicing Method and its Composite Materials

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ABSTRACT

A New type of long length stainless steel fiber is produced by a new production method. In this new process, the stainless steel fiber is produced out of a hot water soluble resin coated coiled thin stainless steel sheet by a new slicing method. This method has high productivity and the stainless steel fiber obtained by this method has uniform and fine diameter. As one of the important characteristics of this method, it is capable that a uniformly mixed different materials fiber can be easily produced with different materials such as metal and plastic polymer sheet, which can be used for various fields of composite materials.

In this manufacturing trial, each specific cutting conditions for fiber production from resin coated stainless steel sheet is investigated. Then, the production of non-woven sheet by means of stainless steel fibers obtained by this method was tried. The non-woven sheets by the present process is applicable to many uses such as sintered bodies, mufflers and filters.

KEYWORDS : Fiber/metallic;Manufacturing;Fiber production;Fiber composite.

1. INTRODUCTION

Excellent in heat and corrosion resistance as well as in chemical

stability and representing metal fibers, stainless steel fiber is widely used as an ordinary fiber material not only, but also for fiber sintered bodies and various fields of composite materials. Stainless steel fiber is mainly produced by wire band drawing method and wire shaving method, the former for 5 - 20 μm and the latter for 30 - 100 μm in fiber diameter respectively. The wire band drawing method, however, has draw-backs such as very expensive and hard to produce fiber of larger diameter. On the other hand, the wire shaving method presents draw-backs such as nonuniformity in obtained fiber diameters, limitation on a kinds of applicable stainless steels.

Authors, who had proposed a production of metal fiber by ordinary coiled sheet slicing method, made experiments of producing fibers of metals such as copper, brass and aluminum to confirm the fact that good quality metal fibers can be obtained inexpensively. It was found, however, that ordinary coiled sheet slicing method applied to the production of stainless steel fiber caused a mutual fusion of sheets on slicing and resulted in a difficulty in obtaining uniformly fine fibers.

Present study was carried out for the purpose of developing a hot water soluble resin coated sheet coil slicing method for obtaining good stainless steel fiber free from mutual fusion between sheets and with uniform fiber diameters. Present report describes the investigation of production conditions of stainless steel fiber by said hot water soluble resin coated sheet coil slicing method, properties of resulted stainless steel fiber and some composite materials obtained from the latter.

2. PRINCIPLE OF RESIN COATED COILED SHEET SLICING METHOD

In Fig.1 is given a metal fiber production process by ordinary coiled sheet slicing method. Production process consists in winding metal sheet in the form of a coil around main machining spindle drum, the end face of the coil being then machined into metal fiber. For obtaining a stainless steel fiber comprising filaments of fine and uniform diameters without mutual fusion between sheets by coiled sheet slicing method, a hot water soluble resin coated sheet coil slicing method was intended to be developed. The hot water soluble resin coated sheet coil slicing method is shown in Fig.2. A sheet coil is coated a hot water soluble resin (solution of 5% PVA) in a film thickness of about 20 μm , dried with heater, wound onto a main spindle in the form of a coil and slicing along the end face of the coil. Resulted product is removed of its resin film through hot water of about 70°C and then provided in the form of wound metal fiber.

FIGURE 1. Schematic of coiled sheet slicing method

FIGURE 2. Hot water soluble resin coating and resin removing

As a coating agent for preventing sheets from mutual fusion in coiled sheet slicing method are considered usual oils, various types of mold releasing agents or the like. Conceivable conditions that coating agents should be provided with are highly effective fusion prevention, easy coating and, in particular, easy removal of coating after fiber slicing or the like. As a result of some investigations, here was applied a hot water soluble resin. As a more simple means, a water soluble resin is conceivable, which, however, was given up for fear of the build up of the resin in a water soluble cutting oil which should be used in the present production method.

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Fusion ratio In Fig. 3 are given the relation between the thickness of applied hot water soluble resin film and fusion ratio. Here the fiber fusion ratio is referred to as $\{(N-n)/N\} \times 100$ (%) wherein N is number of filament (number of coil winding) to be primarily produced and n is actually produced filament number. As a result of the preliminary experimental in ordinary coiled sheet slicing method, fusion ratios ranging from about 43 to

FIGURE 3. Fusion ratio as function of hot water soluble resin film thickness

FIGURE 4. Fusion ratio as function of rake angle, coil sheet thickness and cutting speed

75% were obtained. An applied film thickness of $10 \mu\text{m}$ corresponds to a large fusion ratio of 37%, which represents only a slight effect compared with ordinary coiled sheet slicing method. On the contrary, while a film thickness of $30 \mu\text{m}$ corresponds to a reduction in fusion ratio down to 8%, it produces, however, in the course of cutting a deformation between metal sheet layers and a tucking up at their periphery, which results in a difficulty in obtaining uniform fine diameter filaments. A film thickness of $20 \mu\text{m}$ corresponds to a fusion ratio of about 13%, posing no problems in correction with deformation between metal sheet layers nor with tucking up at their periphery or the like, which confirmed filaments with fine and uniform diameters being obtainable. Accordingly, to the subsequent experiments was applied a constant film thickness of $20 \mu\text{m}$.

In Fig.4 is shown change in fusion ratio with relation to rake angle, sheet thickness, and cutting speed. The fusion ratio is reduced with increasing rake angle, resulting in fine and uniform filaments. With a sheet thickness ranging from $t=0.05$ to 0.1 mm and a cutting speed ranging from 34 to 91 m/min , no significant change in fusion ratio is observed. A rake angle of 10° corresponds to a fusion ratio of about 25%, which prohibits to obtain filaments with fine and uniform diameters. Two factors are consid-

(a) Ordinary coiled sheet slicing (b) Resin coated sheet coil slicing

FIGURE 5. Different appearances of fibers produced by different slicing method

ered responsible thereto; heat generation in the course of cutting and outflow of resin film at fiber producing portion due to heat generation. Rake angles of 25° and 30° correspond to a small fusion ratio of about 13%, which confirmed the production of filaments with uniform and fine diameters. A rake angle of 30° makes cutting edge wear progress in a short time and renders a steady production of fiber difficult.

In Fig.5 are shown different appearances of filaments obtained by ordinary coiled sheet slicing and hot water soluble resin coated sheet coil slicing method. It was confirmed that hot water soluble plastic film which hardly dissolves in such hot water as lower than 50°C would not penetrate into water soluble cutting oil and a film removal treatment as shown in Fig.2 permits to remove the hot water soluble resin coat stuck to fiber almost totally, which facilitates any after-treatment.

3.2 Equivalent diameter of fiber Here was investigated how fine diameter fiber is obtainable by the present process. Since a fiber section obtainable by coiled sheet slicing method is realized by slicing the end face of coiled sheet, it presents a rectangle, one side of which corresponds to the coil sheet thickness and the other depends on the feed rate of tool. In Fig.6 is given a fiber section obtained by the resin coated sheet coil slicing method. In Fig.7 is shown fiber equivalent diameter against feed per revolution for SUS304 coil sheet thickness $t=0.03, 0.05$ and 0.1mm . As a equivalent diameter for a coil sheet thickness $t=0.03\text{ mm}$ and a feed rate of $5\ \mu\text{m}/\text{rev}$, a value of $30\ \mu\text{m}$ was obtained, a good fiber of $100\ \mu\text{m}$ being obtained for $t=0.1\text{ mm}$ and a feed rate of $40\ \mu\text{m}/\text{rev}$. Changing coil sheet

FIGURE 6. Cross section of stainless steel fiber

FIGURE 7. Relation between equivalent diameter and feed rate

thickness and feed rate permits to produce various fibers of any fiber diameter. Moreover, fiber thickness increase ratio against feed rate does not significantly varies depending on the coil sheet thickness, presenting about 2 times for a feed rate of more than $20\ \mu\text{m}/\text{rev}$ and gradually increasing for a feed rate of less than $15\ \mu\text{m}/\text{rev}$ to attain a values about 5 times for a feed rate of $5\ \mu\text{m}/\text{rev}$., which is considered due to the fact that a round worn cutting edge, heat etc. prevented filament from smoothly flowing out, which resulted in a build up of deformation amount.

3.3 A trial of non-woven sheet production Production of non-woven sheet by means of uniform fine diameter stainless steel fibers obtained by hot water soluble plastic coated coil sheet slicing method was tried. The production process of non-woven sheet is shown in Fig.8. For producing non-woven sheet were cut with three pairs of rolls different in revolution speed, which sections were let free fall to conveyor and heaped to constitute non-woven sheet. In Fig.9 are given unit weights of non-woven sheets

FIGURE 8. Non-woven sheet production process

FIGURE 9. Unit weight of non-woven sheet

obtained at various transportation speeds of conveyor carrying filaments cut down from two bundles each comprising 150 filaments of 60 μm diameter and arranged spaced apart 5 cm each other. Three pairs of rollers of a constant revolution of 28, 46 and 580 rpm respectively in the descending order provided a non-woven sheet of 220 g/m^2 at a transportation speed of conveyor of 1 m/min. Changing any number of filament bundles, revolution speed of rollers and transportation speed of conveyor permits to obtain a non-woven sheet of any unit weight.

Resulted non-woven sheet is shown in Fig.10. Favored with an advantage of non-oriented non-woven sheet with any desired unit weight being easily and inexpensively produced, the products by the present process is applicable to many uses such as sintered bodies, mufflers and filters.

FIGURE 10. Production of non-woven sheet and its sintered bodies

4. CONCLUSION

A hot water soluble resin coated sheet coil slicing method, for obtaining stainless steel fibers comprising fine and uniform diameter filaments by resin coated sheet coil slicing method was proposed and an experimental fiber production test was made. As a result, while ordinary coiled sheet slicing method provided a large fiber fusion ratio of at least 43% and was hard to produce fibers of uniform and fine diameters, the application of hot water soluble resin coated sheet coil slicing method permitted to reduce fiber fusion ratio down to 13% with hot water soluble resin film thickness of 20 μm and to confirm the possibility of obtaining fibers with uniform and fine diameters. Moreover, the application of the hot water soluble resin coated sheet coil slicing method permits to obtain fibers of various stainless steels such as austenitic and ferritic stainless steels as well as fibers from such as Ni, other sheet materials susceptible to be fused than stainless steels.